

An Investigation of the Perceptions of the Need for Action Research among Moroccan EFL Teachers:

A Special Reference to EFL High School Teachers in Fez

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Abstract

The present thesis endeavored to investigate the perceptions of the need for action research among Moroccan EFL high school teachers. The major objectives of the study were to find out how widespread are the knowledge and practice of action research among Moroccan EFL teachers and to identify the main obstacles that prevent teachers from engaging in action research. The present thesis comprises three chapters, namely a critical review of the literature which laid down the theoretical and conceptual framework for the study, a methodology chapter which set the methodological guidelines for the data collection and analysis, and a data analysis and discussion chapter in which the obtained data is presented, analyzed and discussed in the light of the research objectives, questions and hypotheses. Triangulation was opted for as an approach for data collection so as to ensure rich as well as valid and reliable data. The total number of participants having taken part in the study is 45 Moroccan EFL teachers from 8 public schools in the city of Fez. The main data collection

instruments used in this study are the questionnaire and the interview. The findings yielded that though in theory most respondents have considerable knowledge of action research, when it comes to practice only a small portion of them (N=11) reported that they did conduct action research. Furthermore, it was also found that though action research is perceived as needed for Moroccan EFL teachers and that almost no one is doubtful about its perceived benefits in solving teaching and learning problems, improving practice and fostering reflection and professional development, Moroccan EFL teachers do not resort to it in order to solve the problems they encounter in their classrooms. Rather the majority of them opt for asking their colleagues and experienced teachers and/or search for a ready-made recipes or external answer as the main strategies they normally they resort to handle the problem arising in their classrooms. The findings of the factors influencing the practice of action revealed that motivation and lack of support are the main inhibiting factors. Concerning the solutions, it was yielded that the promotion of action research is unlikely to occur without enhancing Moroccan EFL teachers' research engagement through pedagogical, practical and financial support in order to address the constraints they are likely to encounter whilst engaging in or initiating such practice. Finally, the findings of this research paper confirm the hypotheses advanced in the study.

Keywords: Action Research, EFL in Morocco, 2nd Language Acquisition.

Introduction and Background to the Study

The introduction of action research in the field of education in general, and second language teaching and learning in particular, has brought about many changes in orientations and foci in educational research. One major shift is changing the conception of research as being the task of researchers only, and as a top-down process undertaken by expert researchers, to a more collaborative and participative process carried out by a teacher or a group of teachers for/with learners (Nunan, 1992; Burns, 1999). The emergence of action research came mainly as an expression of dissatisfaction with the gap that has always existed between theory and practice in research, and as an attempt to move beyond the traditional relationship between the researcher and the practitioner (Makernen, 1991). Another factor for this shift is that practice has revealed that the theories/approaches/methods developed by researchers do not work in all contexts and for all people, or what Stringer (2014) refers to as “one size [that] fits all” formula, simply because the peculiarities of the classrooms differ and so do learners’ needs, styles and strategies. Consequently, these ideas have reoriented the focus of research in Applied Linguistics, and education in general, in such a way that teachers are now called upon to examine their practices and assume the researchers’ role. In this respect, Brown (2001, p. 431) argues that

“The main thing wrong with the world of education today is that there’s this one group of people who do it- the teachers- and then there’s another group who think they know about it- the researchers.”

As a way of bridging the gap between theory and practice when it comes to research, the idea of the teacher as a researcher has become attractive and appealing to many. That is, it has become widely accepted that the classroom research is supposed to be conducted by teachers since it is the teachers who know their classroom context and learners best. Similarly, Brown further argues that *“teachers are the ones who do it [teaching] and, therefore, are the ones who know about it”*

In the same vein, and with the advent of post-method pedagogy, teachers are no longer seen as passive implementers of the conventional methods; instead, teachers are required to assume new reflective and transformative roles. Action research or classroom research is essential in enhancing reflective and transformative teaching in the classroom, through constantly researching their classrooms and engaging in classroom-based research projects in order to solve teaching and learning problems. The post-method teaching emphasizes the role of the teacher in

the construction of his/ her own approach or method of teaching, based on his/ her theoretical, empirical and experiential knowledge (Kumaravadivleu, 1994; Prabhu, 1990 and Richards & Rodgers, 2001). This has led to a redefinition of the role of the teacher from being only a passive practitioner to that of a teacher-researcher.

In light of the above, this study is an attempt to investigate the teachers' perceptions of the need for adopting action research in the Moroccan context, with special reference to Moroccan EFL teachers. The thesis also seeks to find out how widespread the knowledge and practice of action research are among Moroccan EFL teachers.

1. Action Research: an Overview

This section presents a synthesis of the development of the concept of action research (henceforth AR) and is organized around the following sub-sections: first, it provides the main historical and philosophical foundations of action research and second, it presents some definitions of action research, before showcasing the major approaches to action research and the processes involved in it.

1.1. Historical and Philosophical Foundations of Action Research

In the literature, there is no agreement on the exact origins of the concept of action research. Authors such as Kemmis and McTaggart (1988), Burns (1999) and Burns (2005) relate the emergence of action research to the work of John Dewey (1929) and that of the German Gestalt psychologist Kurt Lewin in the mid-1940s. On the one hand, in his work, the progressive educationalist Dewey criticized the way scientific research was carried out in education and called for democratizing educational research by involving practitioners. For Dewey, researchers and practitioners should work together in a participative and democratic way to address educational problems. Accordingly, Burns (1999) maintains that action research

grew out of the moves by progressive educators, such as John Dewey, in the early part of the twentieth century, to challenge the orthodoxy of the scientific research methods current in the field of education (p. 26).

On the other hand, another contribution to the rise of action research was initiated by the German psychologist Kurt Lewin in the USA in the mid-1940s. For Lewin, research should be involved in addressing the crises, conflicts and the problems of social groups in their own environment and within organizations. The thrust of Lewin's ideas, for Burns, is that *"The stimulus to*

enquiry should reside in group social problems investigated within their own practical environment and involving the players within those environment” (p. op. cit. 27). These ideas posed a challenge to the objective social scientific research in favor of a more democratic and problem-solving research. Therefore, Lewin first coined the term ‘action research’ in his 1946 paper “Action Research and Minority Problems”, and then he developed a mode of enquiry that consists of cycles involving analysis, fact-finding, conceptualization, planning, and evaluation. Nevertheless, other scholars such as McKernan (1991), and McNiff (2006) maintain that there is evidence that action research began before the work of Lewin, with the Science in Education Movement in the late nineteenth century. To better understand the origins of action research, it would be more appropriate to provide an overview of the different philosophical foundations that underpin it.

1.2. Defining Action Research

Ever since its inception, the term action research has been defined by different scholars and from different perspectives. For Burns (1999), the word *research* in action research refers to a systematic and scientific investigation, while the word *action* denotes taking practical action or intervention to solve a certain problem or change a situation. A more comprehensive definition of the term “action research” can be found in the Longman Dictionary of Applied Linguistics and Language Teaching and Learning in which action research is defined as a type of:

research that has the primary goal of finding ways of solving problems, bringing about social change or practical action, in comparison with research that seeks to discover scientific principles or develop general laws (Richards, J. C, and Schmidt, 2002, p. 8).

Whereas pure or basic research is concerned with finding out new theories and principles, action research is not concerned with coming up with a new body of knowledge or theories, but rather, it aims at solving practical problems and bringing about change in a situation and in those involved. As Kurt Lewin (1946) puts it, there is “*no action without research, and there is no research without action*” (as cited in Adelman, 1993, p. 8). That is, research should lead to social change; research that produces but books will not suffice (Lewin, 1946 as cited in Burns, 2005). For Kemmis and McTaggard (1988) the ultimate goal for doing action research is to change a system.

Contrary to fundamental or traditional research, action research is conducted in a bottom-up process by the teachers to resolve problematic situations and improve their practice. In this respect,

McKernan (1991) points out that *“The aim of action research, as opposed to traditional or fundamental research, is to solve the immediate and day-to-day problems of practitioners”* (p. 3). In other words, action research provides guiding principles for teachers to research their practices and settings, as well as construct their own living theories of practice. In so doing, teachers will no longer be dependent on outside research or external answers to the problems they encounter in their specific context. Furthermore, action research is understood by many authors as a paradigm of reflective inquiry which has come to bridge the long-standing gap between theory and practice. In action research *“theories are not validated independently of practice and applied to curriculum; rather they are validated through practice”* (p. 4). This, consequently has redefined the traditional role of the teacher from being merely an implementer of the findings of research to that of teacher-researcher.

In a similar vein, and according to Kemmis and McTaggard, action research is defined according to three distinctive characteristics; first, it is a type of research that is carried out by a practitioner, not a researcher; second, it is a collaborative work; third, it aims at bringing about change in a situation. (As cited in Nunan 1992, p. 17). For Richards and Ferrall (2005) action research

takes place in the teacher’s own classroom and involves a cycle of activities centering on identifying a problem or issue, collecting information about the issue, devising a strategy to address the issue, trying out the strategy, and observing its effects (p. 171).

As indicated in this definition, action research starts out of problems or issues the teacher faces in his/ her classroom. It involves making hypotheses, collecting data and systematically analyzing it. An evaluation of the process is required to ensure the validity of the findings and promote continuous self-reflection. The central aim of action research is to solve practical problems and induce change or improvements in a problematic situation, that is, it is a change-oriented process. As McKernan (op. cit. p. 7) rightly puts it, *“Research is action research to the extent that it can solve practical problems.”*

In sum, what is common to all these definitions is the shared view that action research is a break away from a traditional positivist type of research, that it bridges the gap between theory and practice, and that it is undertaken by practitioners to solve practical problems.

1.3. Major Approaches to Action Research

In the literature, action research is commonly approached from many theoretical perspectives. According to McKernan (op. cit.), there are three types of action research, namely Scientific-technical, Practical-deliberative, and Critical-emancipatory, each of which being based on different underlying perspectives and worldviews.

The scientific-technical approach to action research was adopted by early scholars such as Dewey (1929) and Lewin (1946). This view of action research is based on the idea that the researcher and practitioner should collaborate with each other, with the researcher providing the technical knowledge by identifying a problem and designing a pre-determined systematic framework for action/intervention, and the practitioner acting as a facilitator through facilitating the process of research and action (Grundy, 1982 as cited in Masters 1995, n.p). In scientific-technical action research, the nature of the relationship between the researcher and the practitioner is mediatory in that the practitioner's task is to communicate the ideas to the group concerned and help apply them in practice, following scientific procedures determined by the researcher. The aim of this approach is to test existing theories (Holter et al 1993 as cited in Masters, n.p).

The second approach is Practical-deliberative action research. This approach is more collaborative than the scientific-technical one in that the practitioner and researcher mutually decide on all the phases of action research from problem identification to deliberative intervention. The major aim of practical action research is to induce improvements in practice, not just to test existing theories. In this respect, McKernan states that "*The goal of practical action researchers is understanding practice and solving immediate problems*" (p. 20). In this view, the outcomes of action research affect those involved in the process, i.e., the teacher and learners in the classroom.

Based on the aforementioned, in second language teaching and learning, much emphasis has been placed on the second approach of action research which is concerned with solving practical problems and improving practice; however, the critical emancipatory action research is not common in the field of second language teaching (Burns, 2005). Still, in recent years, some trends in applied linguistics such as Critical Applied Linguistics (Pennycook, 2001) have called for more emancipatory and critical approaches to research in language teaching and learning.

Conclusion

Action research is sometimes called teacher research or practitioner research because it is initiated by the teacher in his/her classroom. This type of research was aimed at improving and enhancing social situations in general before it was applied in education to understand and improve the teaching and learning practices in the classroom. Therefore, the present chapter has attempted to

provide a critical review of the literature on the development of action research. This section has presented an overview of the historical foundations, definitions, approaches and different models of action research outlined in the literature.

II. Methodology

Introduction

The previous chapter has presented a critical review of the literature on the issue of action research and the related issues and concepts, as well as the previous studies that were conducted on the issue of action research. The present chapter is concerned with the presentation of the methodology that is followed in the course of data collection and analysis. The chapter also introduces the research design of the present study, the data collection instruments and the ways by which the obtained data is analyzed.

The current chapter is organized as follows: the first section outlines the objectives/ purposes of the study. The second section elaborates on the research hypotheses and questions of the study. In the third section, the targeted population and the context of the study are described. The fourth section deals with the research design adopted in this study. The fifth section describes the main data collection procedures used for data elicitation. Subsequent sections in this chapter deal mainly with the data analysis methods and techniques chosen for this study.

1. The Purpose of the Study

The present study has set as its main objectives to draw attention to an important practice - action research- that teachers can adopt to enhance the teaching and learning process. Therefore, this study is an attempt to investigate the teachers' and trainers' perceptions of the need for adopting action research in the Moroccan context, with special reference to Moroccan EFL teachers. The thesis also seeks to find out how widespread the knowledge and practice of action research are among Moroccan EFL teachers. A further purpose is to investigate the main obstacles that prevent teachers from engaging in action research projects as well as potential solutions or suggestions to overcome those obstacles.

2. Hypotheses and Questions Elaborated

Given that, to the best of the knowledge of the researcher, the only study carried out on the practice of action research, and knowledge and opinions about it, with reference to the Moroccan context, was an international survey by Rainey (2000). In her study, Rainey made

use of a very limited sample (13 questionnaires) which is far from being representative and leave many questions concerning the practice, perceptions and knowledge about action research within the Moroccan context unanswered, particularly that no study, to date, has been conducted within the Moroccan context on the same issue. Therefore, the present study is an attempt to investigate teachers' and trainers' perceptions of the need for action research among Moroccan EFL teachers. As a starting point, this study is premised on the following hypotheses:

- 1) Though action research is likely to be perceived as needed and important for teachers to solve their classroom problems, update their practices and grow professionally, Moroccan EFL teachers do not resort to classroom-based action research to solve classroom and language learning related problems because of their lack of motivation, lack action research skills and time-constraints.
- 2) The more Moroccan EFL teachers attend or engage in professional development activities the more likely they may practice action research

These two hypotheses are based on the researcher's own observation, discussions with some Moroccan high school teachers and knowledge of the nature of the Moroccan education system.

Based on the above hypotheses, this study intends to raise and attempt to answer the following questions:

First question: What are the profiles of Moroccan EFL teachers who conduct/ don't conduct action research?

This question is meant to elicit data from teachers concerning their backgrounds and professional profiles. Answers to this question will vary depending on the experiences and academic and professional achievements of each teacher. The assumption underlying this question is that teachers who hold high degrees and regularly attend professional development activities are likely to demonstrate some knowledge and positive perceptions of action research.

Second question: What are the teachers' the need for action research among Moroccan EFL teachers?

The aim of this question is to elicit the perceptions of high school teachers of/about action research. More specifically, this question will try to highlight how teachers and trainers

conceive of the adoption of action research among Moroccan EFL teachers. Raising this question will allow for a comparison between the perceptions of the Moroccan EFL high school teachers and teacher trainers of the need for action research.

Third question: To what extent is the knowledge of action research widespread among Moroccan EFL teachers?

This question will assess the teachers' awareness and knowledge about action research. Potential answers to the above question will reveal how many of the teachers surveyed know what action research is.

Fourth question: What are the constraints that prevent teachers from engaging in action research?

The above question is meant to find out the main factors that prevent teachers from conducting action research projects either individually or collaboratively with their colleagues. The assumption underlying this question is to reveal the extent to which the Moroccan education system encourages teachers in general, and EFL teachers in particular to engage in such practices as action research.

Fifth question: What is needed to motivate teachers to practice action research?

This question is raised to elicit some practical suggestions from high school teachers and teacher trainers relating to the potential solutions that can motivate teachers to practice action research in their classrooms. Answers to this question are meant to demonstrate the potential solutions that Moroccan EFL teachers think are likely to enhance their motivation to embark on practicing action research and make such a practice a culture among them.

Research variables:

The current study relies on two main variables, i.e., dependent and independent variables. The dependent variable is teachers' practice of action research, while the independent variables are the frequency of the teachers' attendance in professional development activities and teachers' motivation.

Sample of the Study

Before collecting data, selecting an appropriate sample for the study is an essential step for the purposes of context and content validity. This section is devoted to describing the participants in the study and the context where the study is carried out.

Participants in the Study

The sample selected for this study are the English teachers of the city of Fez. The sample consists of a total number of 45 Moroccan EFL teachers. Concerning the sampling technique, probability or random sampling is the technique used for selecting the target sample for this study. According to Kothari (2004, p. 60) “*Probability sampling is also known as ‘random sampling’ or ‘chance sampling’. Under this sampling design, every item of the universe has an equal chance of inclusion in the sample*”. That is to say, this technique of sampling gives the opportunity or the chance for every member of the research group to participate in the study. This technique of sampling was chosen because it is more objective. In addition, this technique yields reliable data that can be generalizable. For Kouthari,

Random sampling ensures the law of Statistical Regularity which states that if on an average the sample chosen is a random one, the sample will have the same composition and characteristics as the universe. This is the reason why random sampling is considered as the best technique of selecting a representative sample. (op. cit)

Figure 1: Respondents’ Background Information

As far as respondents' background information is concerned, both males and females participated in the study and were randomly chosen. As can be seen in the above graph, the number of male teachers (69%) outnumbers that of female teachers (31%). Furthermore, the graph above reflects the range of experience this sample of teachers have. As indicated above, 55, 6 % of the respondents have between 1 and 5 years as a teaching experience. 20% of them have been teaching for more than five years (from 6 to 10). 11. 1% of the participants have a teaching experience of more than 10 years (from 11 to 20). 13, 3% of the respondents have over 20 years as a teaching experience in the Moroccan public schools. This mixture and diversity in terms of the teaching experience among the respondents are likely elicit rich data from them. The participants are also from different educational levels. The majority of respondents hold BA degree because it is the minimum requirement to be recruited in the teaching profession. Besides the BA degree, 24, 4 % of respondents hold MA and 6, 7% are Phd holders.

Context of the Study

This study has been carried out in in the city of Fez where the researcher collected the data from 8 high schools namely. Access to these institutions proved to be a very hard task, especially that some directors/ headmasters refused any administration of the questionnaires without a written permission from "L'Academie Regional des Education".

Research Design

A clear and effective planning of any research necessitates the adoption of an appropriate research design. In any research enterprise, delineating the research design is paramount because it provides the reader with a clear picture of how the study is structured and how its components, ideally, fit together in a coherent and logical way. Therefore, the present study opted for triangulation as the main research design through making use of varied, but complementary, research approaches to ensure both internal and external validity. The mixed-method approach is based on a pragmatic worldview in which

The core assumption of this form of inquiry is that the combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches provides a more complete understanding of a research problem than either approach alone

(Creswell, 2003, p. 32)

For the purpose of triangulation, and in order to elicit tentative answers to the research questions and to test the research hypotheses, both the qualitative and the quantitative approaches were used in this study. The quantitative approach has been helpful in determining the profiles of the teachers who do/ do not use action research, in measuring the extent to which the knowledge and practice of action research is widespread among Moroccan EFL teachers, and in finding out both teachers' perceptions of action research and the different factors that impede its implementation in the Moroccan schools. On the other hand, the qualitative approach has been useful in eliciting more in depth explanations about why some teachers use or do not use action research, how those who practice it use action research, and their perceptions of the need for action research. Therefore, mixing both approaches will increase the validity and the reliability of the data, and thus the quality of the findings.

3. Data Collection Procedures

The data collection procedures are generally determined by the nature of the study and the design adopted. Also, the data elicitation instruments are supposed to be informed by the research objectives and in keeping with the formulated hypotheses and the questions addressed. Therefore, in the present study, the data collection procedures are used to collect rich and reliable data to confirm or disconfirm the hypotheses, potentially answer the research questions and meet the objectives of the research.

Given that the research design / approach used in this study is triangulation, the researcher has opted for the use of two data collection techniques, one is quantitative (the questionnaire) and the other is qualitative (the interview). The questionnaire has been administered to Moroccan EFL high school teachers, while the interview has been conducted with both EFL high school teachers and teacher trainers of the regional centers of education and training in the region of Fez-Meknes.

The questionnaire

The questionnaire is a quantitative data collection instrument used to measure the quantity, amount and frequency of a phenomenon. The questionnaire allows for collecting data from a large sample quickly. As Burns (1999) points out "*Questionnaires have the advantage of being easier and less-time consuming to administer*" (p. 129). One of the strengths of using the questionnaire in this study is to elicit quantitative data related to the background

information, the knowledge, practice, and the perceptions of action research among Moroccan EFL teachers. Yet, one of the weaknesses of this method is that it does not elicit in depth answers from the respondents. To compensate for these weaknesses, the study has opted for another data collection technique, i.e. the semi-structured interview for the purpose of eliciting qualitative data. Therefore, this will increase the reliability and credibility of the findings.

The Interview

Since one of the weaknesses of the questionnaire is its limitation with respect to eliciting in depth information from the respondents, interviews will be used to make up for this and collect more detailed data. This qualitative data collection procedure allows respondents the time and scope express their opinions on a particular subject, and it allows the researcher to elicit in-depth information around the topic. The qualitative data obtained through the use of interviews are used to back up quantitative data and cross check the findings.

The type of interview used in the current study is the semi-structured interview, and the reason behind opting for this type is that it allows flexibility to the interviewer and freedom for the interviewee in answering the questions. According to Nunan (1992, p. 150),

The advantages of the semi-structured interview are, in the first instance, that it gives the interviewee a degree of power and control over the course of the interview. Secondly, it gives the interviewer a great deal of flexibility.

The semi-structured interview is so popular since it is a kind of compromise between the two extremes, i.e., the structured and the unstructured interview. Therefore, the semi-structured type allows the researcher some degree of control by devising guidelines or an agenda for the interview and freedom to the interviewee by including open-ended questions. In this study, the semi-structured interview is administered to Moroccan high school teachers of Fes

III. Data Analysis and Discussion

Introduction:

The previous chapters have provided a critical review of the literature on the development of educational action research and the methodological framework for this study. The current chapter is devoted to the presentation, description and analysis of the data obtained via the data collection instruments used in the light of the research objectives, questions and

hypotheses. The chapter is also concerned with the discussion and interpretation of the findings to draw conclusions and confirm or refute the research hypotheses as well as the implications of the study.

This chapter is organized as follows; the first section discusses the results of the Moroccan EFL teachers' knowledge of action research in order to reveal to what extent is the knowledge of action research widespread among them. The second section analyses the results of the teachers' practice of action research so as to find out whether action research is practiced by Moroccan EFL teachers. The third section is allotted to the discussion of Moroccan EFL teachers' perceptions of the need for action research in Moroccan classrooms. The fourth section tackles the factors influencing the practice of action research and the major constraints that hinder its implementation in the Moroccan context. The fifth section is devoted to the discussion and the interpretation of the findings yielded in the study.

1. Moroccan EFL Teachers' Knowledge of Action Research

This section inaugurates a discussion of the results obtained concerning Moroccan EFL teachers' knowledge of Action Research. The section also attempts to answer the first research question: How widespread is the knowledge of action research among high school Moroccan EFL Teachers? To answer this question, the teachers' knowledge of action research was elicited in three ways. They were first asked about whether they have heard about action research. Then, those who claimed to have heard about it were further asked about the sources of their knowledge and then were provided with three definitions to determine the one that appropriately defines the concept of action research.

The qualitative and quantitative analysis of the data have yielded that the majority of the respondents (82, 2 %) reported that they know about action research. The following graph illustrates the results obtained via the questionnaire on the teachers' knowledge of action research:

Figure 2: Teachers' Knowledge of Action Research

As can be seen in the above graph, 82, 2% of the respondents said 'Yes' when they were asked "have you ever heard of action research?", while only 15,6 % reported that they have never heard of action research. These findings reflect that the knowledge of action research is to a large extent widespread among the Moroccan EFL teachers surveyed. However, and to assess whether this knowledge is based on solid grounds and appropriate or not, the respondents who reported to have heard of action research were given other items to test their knowledge. It is of paramount importance to note that the analysis and discussion that follows will be in terms of the respondents claiming knowledge of action research.

Figure 3: The Source of the knowledge about Action Research

As an attempt to test their knowledge of action research, the respondents who reported that they know about action research were given three definitions and were asked to choose the most accurate definition of action research. The majority of the respondents (77, 8) provided a right answer to the question. The following graph summarizes the findings of the teachers' definitions of action research:

2. Moroccan EFL Teachers' Practice of Action Research

This section discusses the findings of the teacher' practice of action research. It also aims at revealing whether Moroccan EFL teachers practice/ conduct action research in their classrooms or not. The section also shows the frequency of the practice of action research and to check whether Moroccan EFL teachers who reported to practice action research have ever written up and presented their action research projects in professional development activities (e.g. MATE conferences, universities conferences, etc.,).

To elicit data concerning teachers' practice of action research, a section was devoted in the questionnaire to achieve this purpose. The section encompasses various items meant to gain an understanding as to what extent Moroccan EFL teachers engage in action research. The first question the respondents were asked is "Do you conduct action research in your classroom?" Responses to this question are clearly illustrated through the following graph:

Figure 5: Teachers' Practice of Action Research

As indicated in the above graph, 11 (24%) respondents reported that they conducted action research out of 45 Moroccan EFL high teachers surveyed. The respondents who indicated that they conduct action research were asked how frequently they do it. In this regard, the responses of those who conducted action research reported different frequency of practicing it. 5 of them reported that they conduct action research often. 4 of them stated that they do it sometimes. One of the respondents said that he/she always does it and two said that they rarely do it. Graph 7 illustrates the frequency of the practice or engagement in action research among Moroccan EFL teachers:

Figure 6: Frequency of Practice of Action Research

After having reported on the frequency with which they practice action research, the respondents were asked whether they write up their action research works and whether they have ever presented it in a conference, in front of their colleagues or in any other professional development activities. Such questions are meant to see whether they disseminate or share the findings of their research with their colleagues and the wider community through the inspectors' meetings, conferences, MATE circles, etc. This is because the writing and presentation/ dissemination of the findings are integral parts of the processes of action research as well as a characteristic feature of its collaborative principle (see burns, 1999). The graph below shows the results of the writing and presentation of action research among 11 Moroccan EFL teachers who reported that they practiced action research:

Figure 7: Writing and Presentation of Action Research

As the data represented in the above graph indicates, the respondents who conducted action research reported that they did write and present the findings of their action research. On the one hand, all the respondents (11) said that they write up their action research findings. For example, respondent 39 reported that *“I have my teacher portfolio and journal in which I note down my action research and projects to follow development on my teaching philosophy”*. In terms of presenting action research, 6 respondents stated that they have presented their action research, while 5 of them said that they have never presented it in any professional development activity. In this regard, respondent (4) stated that action research *“Needs publication and sharing knowledge”*. This reflects that Moroccan EFL teachers who conduct action research are aware of the importance of sharing/ disseminating the findings of their research.

3. Moroccan EFL Teachers Perceptions of the Need for Action Research

The previous sections have dealt with the description and analysis of the results concerning Moroccan EFL teachers' knowledge about and the practice of action research. The present section discusses the results of the teachers' perceptions of the need for action research among Moroccan EFL teachers. The section presents and analyzes the results obtained via the two main data collection instruments employed in this study.

Figure 8: The Need for Action Research among Moroccan EFL Teachers

As can be seen in the above graph, a total number of 43 teacher (95, 6 %) reported that action research is needed among Moroccan EFL teachers and only 2 teachers (4, 4 %) said that it is not needed. These findings demonstrate that the overall perceptions of Moroccan EFL teachers are positive and also reflect an appreciation of the usefulness of action research. This is so because it is widely believed that such type of research will be useful in helping Moroccan teachers to raise the bars and standards of the teaching and learning practices. An evidence for this argument can be found in the testimony of the respondent 8 who bluntly stated that *“It is needed so that teachers could study problems, find solutions to them. Also, it helps improve the performance of teachers”*. In the same vein, respondent 19 argued that *“the teaching of English as foreign language in Morocco needs improvement, so I believe action research is the key to find solutions for teachers’ problems, hence improve the teaching learning process of English”*. It becomes clear from these testimonies that action research is perceived to be the key to solve classroom problems and ultimately improve the teaching and learning practices in the Moroccan schools. Following the same stream of thought, respondent 6 stated that: *“ Because the classroom today is full of problems which should be solved; the key to this is action research”*. Similarly, respondent 7 stressed that *“There is a dire need for action- oriented research in our Moroccan classrooms. Problems inside the classrooms should solved by teachers themselves”*. Furthermore, it is also believed that action research can empower teacher and make them participate effectively in reforming and improving the quality of the educational system at large. For example, respondent 18 clearly stated that

“Practitioners should be given the opportunity to contribute to the improvement of the educational system through action research”. In a similar vein, respondent 19 arguably stated that *“Action Research is something teachers should be encouraged to do and practice for the better of their own teaching and students learning. Teachers should work collaboratively through communities to help, share ideas and thus suggest solutions and develop professionally.”*

Figure 9: Should Action Research Become Mandatory for EFL Teachers

As is illustrated in the above graph, the data demonstrates that a good number of respondents seem to be against the idea that action research should be made a mandatory activity and part and parcel of their duties as teachers. Though results show that 55, 4 % of them said “Yes” and the rest 44, 4 % said “No, the qualitative data elicited some staunch reactions against the idea of making action research mandatory for Moroccan EFL teachers. To back up this argument, respondent 19 (female) when asked to justify why action research should be mandatory, she stated that *“It should be left for the teacher to choose whether to conduct action research or not depending on his/ her needs (the problems they have)”*. In a similar vein, respondent 15 (male) argued that though action research is needed to help teachers solve problems, it should not be imposed. To quote his words, *“It is preferable when approaching a teaching /learning problem, not obligatory though”*.

“Definitely, it is for me, personally speaking, it is a must, not just needed, because when we get into the educational domain first we go from novice teachers to somewhat trained teachers or experienced teachers. And as you go along, you face

problems and these problems need analysis, need, I would say, unveiling in order to remedy them. This is why we have to use, or have to conduct action research in order to describe, analyze and eventually to solve the problems.”

Since the aforementioned items were meant to reveal the extent to which the respondents believe that action research is need among Moroccan EFL teachers, the participants were asked to rate pre-determined statements using the attitudinal scale “Strongly Agree”, “Agree”, “Neutral”, “Disagree” and “Strongly Disagree” as a check to the previous items. This scale was meant to elicit more insights and data with regards to their perceptions of the need for action research as a type of the practitioner research. The graph below displays the results obtained on Moroccan perceptions of action research:

Figure 10: Moroccan EFL Teachers' Perceptions of Action Research

As can be noted from the above graph, the respondents were given 9 statements to rate using “Strongly Agree”, “Agree”, “Neutral”, “Disagree” and “Strongly Disagree”. As far as the first statement is concerned, most respondents agree that “Teachers should conduct action research”. Secondly, the majority of respondents agree and most of them strongly agree with the statement that “Action research helps solve teaching and learning problems”. Thirdly, the majority of the respondents reported that they “strongly agree” and “agree” with the statement

that “Action research fosters reflective teaching most of them”. Fourthly, most respondents remained neutral about the statement “Teachers who conduct action research are better than those who do not”, while others either agree or strongly agree. Fifthly, the majority of the respondents reported that they agree and strongly agree with idea that “action research fosters teachers’ professional development”. Sixthly, the utmost majority reported that they disagree and strongly disagree with the statement that “Action research is of no use at all”. Seventhly, the majority agrees and strongly agrees with the statement that “Moroccan education system does not encourage action research”. The majority remained neutral about the eight statement the respondents were asked to rate that “Action Research is widely adopted by Moroccan EFL teachers”. Lastly, the majority of the respondents agree and strongly agree with the statement that “Moroccan teachers should become classroom researchers”, while only a small portion of them remained neutral.

The following graph shows the results of the teachers’ dominate strategies to deal with teaching learning problems:

Figure 11: The dominant Strategies to deal with teaching and learning problems among Moroccan Teachers

As one can see in the above graph, when teachers were provided by a scenario in which they are asked about the first strategy they normally employ to deal with a problem facing them in their classrooms, the first chosen is strategy by most respondents is “ask your colleagues and/or experienced teachers for help”, the second chosen strategy is “look for external

answers by reading a book or searching on the internet”, the third chosen strategy is “start an action is to start an action research to solve the problem by yourself “.This implies that Moroccan EFL teachers tend to depend on external answers/remedies/recipes to the problems they encounter in their specific environment and that they prefer to ask their colleagues and surf the net than taking the trouble of launching a classroom action research to solve the problem by themselves.

4. Constraints and Solutions

Given that the previous three sections have been concerned with the description and the analysis of the obtained data related to the teachers’ knowledge, practice and perceptions of action research, it follows, then, that the current section deals with presenting and analyzing the results of the main factors/ reasons that prevent teachers’ from conducting action research. It is the potential solutions that are likely to promote action research among Moroccan EFL teachers as well as to enhance their motivation to practice it.

4.1.Constraints:

The data analyzed in the previous sections revealed that there is a huge gap between teachers’ knowledge of action research and their practice of it. That is, most Moroccan EFL teachers surveyed demonstrated a considerable knowledge of action research; however, very small portion of them reported that they practiced action research from time to time. In this respect, so as to find out about the main reasons behind their lack of engagement in action research, the questionnaire included an item in which the respondents were provided with 8 constraints/reasons/factors and asked to choose the ones which they think impede/hinder their practice or implementation of action research in their classrooms. The graph below shows the results of the respondents’ answers to the factors that hinder the practice of action research:

Figure 12: Factors which Hinder the Practice of Action Research among Moroccan EFL Teachers

As the data obtained indicates, the first chosen factor is lack of motivation. Most respondents opted for the lack of motivation as the main inhibitor that impedes the practice of action research among Moroccan EFL teachers. In fact, motivation needs to be present in any activity to succeed. If one is not motivated, one will be unwilling to engage in any practice or activity. Lack of support from the ministry is the second chosen factor that is likely to hinder the practice of action research by Moroccan EFL teachers. As a matter of fact, one of the most frequently cited reason used by teachers to justify their lack of engagement in action research is that they are paid to teach and not to do research. In other words, teachers believe that for them to practice action research they should receive support/ incentives from the ministry or the school in which they work. That is, why should they bother themselves doing something they have not been assigned to do in the first place?

Potential Solutions

After having discussed the main factors behind Moroccan EFL teachers lack of practice and/or engagement in action research, this sub-section presents the results of the potential solutions that are likely to enhance Moroccan EFL high school teachers' motivation to practice action research in their classrooms. The objective of the present section is to analyze

the obtained data in order to suggest ways to address the constraints of action research discussed previously.

To elicit data concerning the most potential solutions that respondents think are to be useful in motivating EFL teachers to engage action research and promote this practice, the respondents were supposed to rank 5 solutions, namely “the government should provide incentives”, “the lack of support from the ministry/ school”, “the ministry of education should provide training on action research”, “action research should become an essential part of the training program”, “teachers should take initiatives by establishing units of research in their schools devoted for action research” and “action research should be made on the criteria for teachers’ promotion” respectively from the most potential (1) to the least potential (5). The following graph highlights the ranking of the solutions from the most potential to the least potential:

Figure 13: Potential Solutions to enhance Moroccan EFL Teachers’ Motivation to Practice Action Research

A close analysis of the above graph revealed that “the government should provide incentives” and funds to Moroccan EFL teachers to enhance their motivation to practice action research is the first ranked potential solution by most respondents (43%). As was indicated earlier, the lack of support from the ministry/ school was regarded as the second chosen constraint that hinder the practice of action research. That is why it is believed by the respondents that it is

essential to support students and motivate them extrinsically through providing me with incentives and comfortable working conditions. As interview 1 put it:

“I think the ministry of education should or must provide us with the funds, the financial support and everything that we need in order to conduct such research because it is not theoretical or conceptual but we should do field work, we should do experiment. This ... also needs the environment of teaching should be helpful, it should conducive... I mean... to conduct such a research, so that the teachers will be very motivated, very enthusiastic”

However, the ministerial support does not necessarily have to be always material. As an evidence for this interview 2 said

“I think the ministry has a say here; the ministry of education has something to do here; suppose I have done research; I come up with certain results; it is true that these results are going to help me in settling many problems in my classroom; but it could be so encouraging like if the ministry gives me some credits and takes these findings into account and recommend them. Legal accreditation from the ministry because when you give support and acknowledgement to certain; I am sure that this work is going to be frequent. It is going to be held by many teachers.”

5. Discussion and Interpretation of the Findings

To gain understanding as to why the practice of action research is not common among Moroccan EFL high school teachers, the study has attempted to investigate the main factors influencing their lack of engagement in research and the potential solutions that are likely to promote action research among Moroccan EFL teachers as well as to enhance their motivation to practice it. On the one hand, and to reveal the major factors behind the lack of action research practice, the respondents were provided by a list of possible factors and asked to choose the ones they think that hinder the implementation of action research. The findings yielded that most respondents opted for the lack of motivation as the main inhibitor that impedes the practice of action research among Moroccan EFL teachers. Other factors include lack of support from the ministry/ school, lack of training, lack time and timetable pressures, lack of resources, lack of research skills, etc.,. These factors can be categorized into internal and external factors. Internal factors relate to the willingness and motivation to practice it, while external factors relate to the unfavorable teaching conditions. In fact, these factors are closely related in the teachers' motivation and willingness

can be enhanced through providing them with favorable conditions to effectively engage in action research. On the other hand, and to address those factors, the teachers were asked to rank the possible solutions to enhance their motivation to practice research from the most potential to the least potential.

Based on the above discussion and interpretation of the findings, it is paramount to see the extent to which the research objectives have been met, the research questions have been potentially answered and the postulated research hypotheses have been confirmed or disconfirmed. Concerning the research objectives, the study was to a large extent able to reveal the perceptions of the Moroccan EFL teachers of the need for action research, to find out about their knowledge and the practice of action research and to identify the major factors influencing it and the potential solutions to address them. Regarding the research questions, the study has tentatively answered most questions that have been raised in the beginning of the study, namely what are the teachers' perceptions of action research? How widespread is the knowledge and practice of action research among Moroccan EFL teachers? What are the constraints that hinder the implementation of action research among Moroccan EFL teachers? What is needed to enhance Moroccan EFL teachers' motivation to practice action research? As far as the research hypotheses are concerned, the study was premised on two hypotheses. The first one was completely confirmed which is:

3) Though action research is likely to be perceived as needed and important for teachers to solve their classroom problems, update their practices and grow professionally, Moroccan EFL teachers do not resort to classroom-based action research to solve classroom and language learning related problems because of their lack of action research skills and time-constraints.

The second one was also confirmed which is:

4) The more Moroccan EFL teachers attend or engage in professional development activities the more likely they may practice action research

Since this study attempted to investigate the perceptions of the need for action research among Moroccan EFL teachers, the argument put forward is that this practice should constitute a vital part of the teaching and learning process. That is, action research should be seen as a part and parcel of the teaching process, not an additional workload the teacher should do.

Conclusion:

This chapter has presented, analyzed and discussed the quantitative and qualitative data collected via the data the research instruments used in the study. The chapter has been divided into five sections. The first section has tackled the Moroccan EFL high teachers' knowledge of action research. The second section has been concerned with presenting and analyzing the data obtained on the teachers' practice of action research. The third section has analyzed the teachers' perceptions of the need for action research among Moroccan EFL teachers. The fourth section has analyzed the factors that affect the teachers' practice of action research and the potential solutions likely to address them. Finally, the last section has been devoted to the discussion and the interpretation of the findings revealed in the study.

General Conclusion

The present thesis endeavored to investigate the perceptions of the need for action research among Moroccan EFL high school teachers. Besides attempting to analyze Moroccan EFL teachers' perceptions of the need for adopting action research, other major objectives were to find out about the knowledge and practice of action research among Moroccan EFL teachers and to reveal the main obstacles that prevent teachers from engaging in action research projects. To achieve this, the thesis was composed of three chapters. The first chapter has been provided a critical review of the literature on the development of action research in the field of education in general and language teaching and learning in particular. Then the chapter presents an overview of the different approaches to, and views on, action research, drawing on both theoretical and empirical studies. It also attempts to establish a link between action research and current issues in second language education namely post-method pedagogy, professional development, and autonomy. The second has set the methodological framework for this study. The chapter has stated the research objectives and elaborated on the research hypotheses and questions to set the guidelines for the data collection methods. Then the participants and the context of the study have been described. The chapter has also provided a detailed description of the design adopted and the data collection methods used, namely, the questionnaire and the interview. Subsequent

sections of this chapter have presented and discussed the data analysis methods and the tools used for the descriptive/statistical analysis. The third chapter has been devoted to the presentation, description and analysis the data obtained via the data collection instruments used in the light of the research objectives, questions and hypotheses. The chapter has also been concerned with the discussion and interpretation of the findings to draw conclusions and confirm or refute the research hypotheses as well as the implications of the study.

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